

**A methodological study of adhesion dynamics in a batch culture of the marine
microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana***

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Abstract

This paper addresses a complete set of procedures to study and to better understand the emerging problem of the biofouling formation in PBRs. Methodologies are described in detail for: (i) PBR and microalgae mat surface preparation, (ii) contact angles (CA) and zeta potential (ZP) measurements for both microalgal cells and PBR surfaces, and (iii) microscopic methods for studying the evolution of adhesion intensity. The impact that these methodologies may have on the photosynthetic apparatus of the cells, the biomass concentration and cell viability are also quantified. A lab-scale flat-plate PBR was used to perform a long-term batch culture of the marine microalgae *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, in which a devised rack of 25 PBR glass surfaces were submerged. To study the cell-to-cell and cell-to-PBR surface interactions, the existing surface thermodynamics and colloidal theories (XDLVO) were used. The major outcomes were: (1) that *N. gaditana* has a exposure time threshold to the electric field produced by the ZP meter; (2) a linear equation is provided for predicting the PBR surface potential as a function of the culture medium's ionic strength; (3) the biofouling growth curve on the PBR surface varied in line with the growth kinetic followed by the freely suspended culture cells; (4) the devised PBR slide rack system offers a versatile experimental platform for generating biofouling results, making it suitable for the *in situ* efficiency evaluation of antibiofouling coatings; (5) there was a significant variation in the surface free energy of the PBR surfaces and algal mats with respect to that present at the beginning of the culture, and, consequently, the application of thermodynamic theories failed to predict cell adhesion over long-term cultivation. However, the XDLVO model satisfactorily explained the dynamics of the adhesion studied. The reported results might be useful for research in the microalgal production and PBR engineering area.

Keywords: *Nannochloropsis gaditana*; adhesion; thermodynamic model; XDLVO
model; photobioreactor; biofouling

1. Introduction

It is widely-recognized that biofouling causes significant problems in closed photobioreactors (PBRs) and, to a lesser extent, in open ponds. Prevention of microalgal adhesion on the inner walls of closed PBRs is a critical step in improving the performance of the photosynthetic microalgae bioprocess, and in reducing operating costs. Understanding the factors governing microalgal attachment on PBR surfaces is a key issue in selecting materials and surface coatings suitable for manufacturing PBRs based on the species to be cultured.

Notwithstanding, the studies hitherto reported on microalgal biofouling formation are scarce, performed only at lab scale and mainly using diatoms and freshwater Chlorophyceae focused on fields other than microalgal biotechnology [1-7]. Nonetheless, the conclusions derived using contact angle measurements of test liquids via Young's equation [8] are contradictory. The application of the extended Derjaguin, Landau, Verwey, Overbeek model (XDLVO) [9] in recent comprehensive studies has improved our understanding of cell-to-cell and cell-to-surface interactions for different microalgae species [10-12].

The main drawbacks of these studies are: (i) the small operational scale (<500 ml); (ii) a very short time scale for the adhesion experiments (2-24h) compared to the temporal operating scale of industrial PBRs (weeks to years); (iii) a flawed methodology in addressing studies with marine microalgae – this is due to the inaccurate description of the surface zeta potential determination for seawater-based culture media (i.e. high ionic strength); and (iv), the fluid dynamics existing in the culture systems used were very different from those inside pilot- or large-scale PBRs.

This work addresses the aforementioned drawbacks by means of the following objectives: (i) reporting a complete set of revised procedures to measure the physico-

chemical properties of the microalgae surface, the substrata and the biofilm formation;

(ii) evaluating the influence of selected methodological aspects for measuring surface zeta potential, ZP, (i.e. the duration of the electric field applied, the ionic strength of the culture medium and the microalgal cell concentration) on photosynthetic parameters and cell viability as reliability indicators for a standardized measurement procedure; (iii) applying thermodynamics and XDLVO approaches to model surface interactions between algal cells and substrata; and (iv) validating the predictions of the models with experimental data obtained from long-term cultivation of *Nannochloropsis gaditana* in a laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor. *Nannochloropsis* is considered a potential biorefinery feedstock [13]. Microscopic glass slides arranged in plastic racks inside the PBR were used as test surfaces for cell adhesion.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Species, culture conditions and culture system

Monocultures of the microalga *N. gaditana* B-3 were used. The strain was provided by the Marine Culture Collection at the Andalusian Institute of Marine Sciences (CSIC, Cádiz, Spain). Inocula were grown photoautotrophically in 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks containing 700 mL of culture under continuous illumination at 25 °C; this illumination being provided by 58W fluorescent lamps rendering an average irradiance at the culture flask surface of 100 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Cultures were agitated by gas sparging with filtered gas from a compressor, injected through a sparger nozzle at an aeration rate of 0.5 $\text{v v}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$. The culture medium was prepared from natural, filter-sterilized (0.22 μm Whatman GF/F 47 mm, Maidstone, The United Kingdom) Mediterranean seawater; this was used to maintain the inocula in all subsequent experiments. The culture medium composition has been reported elsewhere [14].

A laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor (LS-PBR) was used as culture system. The LS-PBR was custom built to a design that was based on experience gathered with similar outdoor industrial-scale flat-panel photobioreactors, in which the existence of significant biofouling was confirmed [15, 16, 17]. The LS-PBR consisted of a u-shaped disposable plastic bag located between two iron frames, 0.09 m apart. The frames and plastic bag were 0.305 m high and 0.53 m long. The plastic bag was made of free-dispersant 0.75 μm polyethylene, with a 0.95 transparency index in the photosynthetically active spectrum. A double-nozzle sparger (1 mm hole diameter and 4 cm distance between holes) was placed in the bottom center of the plastic bag for aeration (0.5 v/v min). The culture volume was fixed at 12 L. The gas-free liquid height was 0.26 m at the beginning of the culture. The aspect ratio height to width (H/W) of the LS-PBR was as low as 0.5 to provide a pseudo-steady-state liquid flow regime characterized by a simple stationary bubble jet that rises vertically upward, forming two symmetric liquid circulation vortex as reported elsewhere for H/W values lesser than or equal to 1 [18-20]. Both liquid vortexes could be visually observed and the algal suspension flowed upward in the center of the PBR (in the wakes of the rising bubbles) and downward along the vicinity of the walls. The complete details of the culture system appear in the Figure 1.

The LS-PBR was frontally illuminated on both sides with up to 10 fluorescent lamps (Osram Dulux PRO Mini Twist 23W-840 E27, China). The irradiance on the photobioreactor surface was measured using a QSL-100 quantum scalar irradiance sensor (Biospherical Instruments, San Diego, USA). In order to recreate the environmental conditions that promote biofouling, an averaged photosynthetically active irradiance of 1200 $\mu\text{mol photons E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and a temperature of 26 ± 1 °C were set. The culture temperature was controlled by circulating thermostatically-controlled water

through a heat exchanger consisting of a 1.8 m long, 6.4 mm inner diameter stainless steel tube. The pH was controlled at 8.0 ± 0.1 by automatic injection of carbon dioxide into the culture, as needed. The sparger used for injecting carbon dioxide was separate from the earlier-mentioned air sparger. This prevented CO_2 mixing with the air and enhanced CO_2 mass transfer. To mitigate the effects of culture evaporation, the salinity of the culture medium was controlled at around 45 mS cm^{-1} by supplementing it with distilled water, as needed.

Figure 1. Schematic of the laboratory-scale flat-panel (LS-PBR) photobioreactor (dimensions in cm): (A) Front view; (B) Section viewed from the top. The gas is sparged at the bottom. Microscopy glass slides are vertically deposited in plastic racks submerged inside the culture. Arrows symbolize gross flow pattern of the culture.

Prior to introducing the culture, the photobioreactor was cleaned as reported elsewhere [21]. After this, the LS-PBR was filled with culture medium. A 7 L volume of fresh medium was inoculated using a 5 L-sized inoculum that was in the late exponential growth phase. The biomass concentration in the freshly-inoculated bioreactor was approximately 100 mg L^{-1} .

Microscopic glass slides (Normax, Ref. 54 702 08A, Portugal; 26x76 mm) were used as test surfaces for cell adhesion. Slides were arranged in a plastic rack with an open bottom (Deltalab, Ref. 191100, Spain) holding a maximum of 25 single slides (see Fig. 1), with a distance between slides of 2 mm. The rack was placed inside the photobioreactor close to the culture-free surface in a vertical position to ensure rapid draining of the culture through the space between the slides. A batch culture was then started (Stage 1). Once the stationary growth phase was reached, the culture was replenished with the specified medium formulation and a new stationary phase was allowed to re-establish (Stage 2). The replenishment was carried out by removing a 0.5 L volume of the broth and replacing it with an equal volume of medium stock solution with a concentration of nutrients equivalent to the whole culture volume of the PBR (i.e. 12 liters). The biomass concentration of the culture was estimated spectrophotometrically by measuring the absorbance at 540 nm (Helios Omega UV–VIS Spectrophotometer, Thermo Scientific, Horsham, England) and it was verified by dry weight measurements as proposed elsewhere [22]. The physiological status of the cells was determined by the maximum photochemical yield of photosystem II (PSII) as described previously [23], estimated as the ratio between the maximum variable fluorescence (F_V) and the maximum fluorescence (F_M) of chlorophyll, F_V/F_M .

2.2. Preparation of adhesion surfaces

Before being placed inside the LS-PBR, the microscopic glass slides were prepared as described elsewhere [24]. In short, the slides were cleaned in 2.7 M HCl for 5 h, rinsed with deionized water (DI), and then treated with ultrasound (280W, 50 Hz) in 1% Alconox solution (Alconox Inc., Alconox, NY), ethanol and acetone (10 min for each). Following this, the slides were rinsed with DI and air-dried.

2.3. Contact angle measurement

According to the extended XDLVO model equations listed in the appendix, the surface energy of the microalgal cells and the substrate (i.e. the microscope glass slide) was estimated from contact angle (CA) values. The CA measurements were carried out using the sessile drop technique. The polar liquids - water and formamide, and the apolar liquid, diiodomethane, were employed as reference liquids. The use of these liquids for determining the CA of different microorganisms has been recently reviewed [11].

The CA measurements were conducted in a goniometer (Drop Shape Analyzer DSA25, KRÜSS GmbH, Germany). Microalgal lawns of 7×10^6 cells mm^{-2} were prepared as follows. Sufficiently-concentrated culture samples were centrifuged. The pellets formed were washed twice with an ammonium carbonate solution (39.8 g L^{-1}) and centrifuged to remove supernatants. The pellets were resuspended in 5 mL of deionized water and finally filtered through $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ mixed cellulose acetate filters (Sartorius Stedim Biotech GmbH, Germany). In order to stabilize the moisture content, the obtained microalgal lawns were then placed for 30 min in a Petri plate over 1% agar (W/v), prepared with 10% (v/v) glycerol in water. The excess moisture was removed after 50 min at 26°C and a lawn thickness above $200 \mu\text{m}$ was observed. At this point, all the CA values attained plateau region.

The CA measurements of both algal lawns and glass slides were carried out at 25°C with $5 \mu\text{L}$ droplets of each reference liquid at different locations. The stabilization time for the probe liquids on the lawns and slides ranged from 1 to 2 s and readings were recorded between 2 and 10 s after depositing them on the lawns and slides, respectively. The algal lawn samples were prepared in triplicate. To monitor the CA

evolution on the glass slides submerged in the photobioreactor, two of them (i.e. two replicates) were drawn out every 2 days, rinsed with deionized water and dried on a Petri plate as detailed above. A minimum of two droplets of probe liquid were deposited on each samples. At least 20 measurements for each droplet of probe liquid were performed.

2.4. Zeta potential measurement

The zeta-potential (ZP) measurements of the *N. gaditana* cells (ζ_m) and the slide glass (ζ_s) were made with a Zetasizer Nano ZS device (Malvern, UK) equipped with a He-Ne laser (633 nm) as the light source. The Zetasizer uses the laser doppler velocimetry (LDV) method (also known as Laser Doppler Electrophoresis) linked to the phase analysis light scattering technique (PALS) and the fast and slow electric field changes in an M3 system (Zetasizer Nano Series User Manual, 2004). The LDV method is used to determine electrophoretic mobility (ζ_m) of cells in an electric field. The ζ_m values of the cells were quantified using the Henry equation:

$$\xi_m = \frac{\varepsilon \cdot \zeta_m}{\eta} \cdot f(\kappa a) \quad (1)$$

where ε is the dispersing medium permittivity, η is the dispersing medium viscosity and $f(\kappa a)$ is Henry's function. This equation is valid for any particle shape, provided that the (local) curvature radius, a , exceeds the Debye length κ^{-1} , i.e. $a\kappa \gg 1$ [25]. We used Smoluchowski's approximation, i.e. $f(\kappa a) = 1$. Its use is restricted to suspensions of (non-conducting) large particles ($>0.2 \mu\text{m}$) in aqueous solutions of relatively high salt (electrolyte) concentration ($>1 \text{ mM}$), such as those for bacteria or microalgae [26, 27] (Zetasizer Nano Series User Manual, 2004).

A general purpose protocol is used in the device's software. Thus, ζ determination is achieved by placing a microalgal suspension in a disposable "size and

zeta potential” folded capillary cell (Green cell, Malvern, UK), using a maximum of 50 repeated measurements on the same sample. Each measurement time was 0.95 s. An analysis of fast and slow electric field changes provided information regarding the mean value and the zeta potential distribution. For all the measurements, the following dispersing medium parameter values were set: (i) the microalgal absorption and refractive indexes were 0.76 and 1.349, respectively; (ii) a seawater refraction index of 1.341 was estimated from equations reported in the literature [28]; (iii) the dielectric constant for seawater at the working temperature (26°C) was calculated from Klein’s equation [29]; (iv) the algal suspension viscosity measured with a Cannon-Fenske viscometer was $0.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$ Pa s; (v) the algal suspension bulk density measured using a pycnometer was 1023 Kg m^{-3} . The zeta potential and electrolytic conductivity (C) were measured simultaneously. For C values lower than 5 mS cm^{-1} , a 150 V voltage and a 5 mA current were used. For media with higher conductivity, a lower voltage was applied automatically by the software (Zetasizer Nano technical note), except when C was above 30 mS cm^{-1} , which resulted in poor phase plot quality. In this case, a 50 V voltage and 31.2 mA current were set manually.

Microalgal suspensions were prepared before being placed in the folded capillary cell as follows. Culture samples were centrifuged at 3260 g for 7 min. Pellets were then resuspended in supernatant until reaching a cell concentration of between 4×10^6 and 3×10^7 . This operational range was selected after a previous assay with *N. gaditana* suspensions of varying cell concentrations. The dilutions were prepared in triplicate using the same supernatant providing a final conductivity value of $45 \pm 5 \text{ mS cm}^{-1}$, equivalent to an ionic strength (I) of around 540 mM (a value above the operational limit of the folded capillary cell) and a pH value of 8.03. The temperature was 26 ± 0.1 °C. Figure 2 shows the effect of dilution on the corresponding zeta-potential

values. As can be seen, below 4×10^6 cells mL^{-1} , the Zetasizer did not meet the quality criteria and the zeta potential decreased as the cell concentration increased. Above this threshold concentration, changes in zeta potential were insignificant and the zeta-potential measurements were identified by the Zetasizer as being accurate.

Figure 2. The effect of cellular concentration used in the folded capillary cell of the Zetasizer on the zeta-potential of *N. gaditana* (ζ_m). Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation (SD) for triplicate samples. Values denoted by a different lowercase at each point differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ in one-way ANOVA. When the DE bar is absent, the SD is smaller than the point.

In order to rule out any effect from ZP measurement repetitions (i.e. the number of sub-runs) on microalgae, the cell population deposited in the folded capillary cell was immediately analyzed before and after the ZP measurement using three methods: (i) flow cytometry; (ii) the maximum photochemical photosystem II (F_V/F_M) yield; and (iii) the rapid light curve (RLC) technique [30] to measure the photosynthesis-light response curves. After an initial F_V/F_M measurement in cells that had been dark-acclimated for 30 min, RLCs were performed using a 27 s exposure at each actinic light level. A complete

RLC consisted of calculating photosynthetic activity estimated as the relative electron transport rate ($rETR$) at incremental irradiances, E (0, 10, 60, 140, 242, 411, 661, 997, 1381, and 1963 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The $rETR$ vs E curves were constructed using the Eilers and Peeters model [31]:

$$rETR = \frac{E}{x_1 E^2 + x_2 E + x_3} \quad (2)$$

where x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 are the model's adjustment parameters. The photosynthetic parameters: α (photosynthetic rate in the light-limited region), E_k (saturating irradiance), and $rETR_{max}$ (relative maximum electron transport rate) were determined according to the following equations:

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{x_3} \quad (3)$$

$$rETR_{max} = \frac{1}{x_2 + 2\sqrt{x_1 x_3}} \quad (4)$$

$$E_k = \frac{x_3}{x_2 + 2\sqrt{x_1 x_3}} \quad (5)$$

Curve fitting was accomplished using SigmaPlot v6. All measurements were carried out in duplicate samples and average value was used.

To quantify the substrate's surface ZP (i.e. the glass slide), the electro-osmotic flow mapping method was used, as described elsewhere [32]. A dip cell type device, ZEN1020, (Malvern, UK) was used in the Zetasizer. The device consists of a height-adjustable sample barrel, in which a tiny 4x8 mm² rectangular piece of the substrate, no more than 1.5 mm in thickness, was glued onto a sample holder and held between two palladium electrodes. The sample barrel was submerged in a 1.3 cm³ conventional cuvette containing a *N. gaditana* suspension prepared at the optimal cell concentration, as described above. The surface zeta potential determination was then performed at

different distances from the sample holder to the bottom. This distance was controlled by moving the substrate holder's vertical position using the adjuster at the top of the cell. Tracer particles comprised of single microalgal cells were used. A new microalgae suspension was prepared and used for the measurement at each distance (a preliminary study had demonstrated that the ZEN1020's palladium electrodes had to be cleaned after each measurement).

Measurements were made at distances ranging from 62.5 μm to 625 μm . A electric field applied via the electrodes initiated electrophoresis of the microalgal cells. The closer the microalgae were to the substrate surface, the bigger the effect of electro-osmosis on the microalgae's mobility. As the distance of microalgal cells from the substrate surface increased, the effect of the electrophoresis increased. The measured electrophoretic mobility varied as a linear function of distance up to the point at which microalgae movement was entirely dependent on electrophoresis (ξ_m). By plotting the ZP reported for the cells (ζ_m), as a function of displacement from the substrate holder, the zeta potential at the substrate surface (ψ_s) was then calculated by extrapolating the graph to zero displacement and applying the following formula:

$$\psi_s = -\text{intercept} + \zeta_m \quad (6)$$

where ζ_m is the cells' zeta potential recorded far from the wall; here, the electro-osmotic flow can be taken as zero. The rationale of this equation has been comprehensibly reported [32]. All measurements were carried out in duplicate samples and an average value was used.

The influence of ionic strength (I) on ψ_s and ζ_m is well-documented [33, 34]. However, the maximum values of I reported in the literature are around 100 mM, near the limit value established in the majority of zeta potential meters, and much lower than that in Mediterranean seawater ($I= 680$ mM, equivalent to a C value of 56 mS cm^{-1}),

which is used as the basis of the culture medium. A series of experiments were conducted to evaluate the effect of I on the surface zeta potential. The I values ranged from 0.36 mM (0.03 mS cm⁻¹) to 107.8 mM (9.1 mS cm⁻¹). The results obtained were used to forecast surface zeta potentials at I values significantly above 100 mM.

2.5. Analytical procedures

In experiments to set up the zeta potential protocol (see subsection 2.4), we evaluated the effect of exposure time (i.e. the number of sub-runs) and the electric field intensity on cell counting and viability using flow cytometry (CellLabQuanta SC, Beckman Coulter). The settings on the three detectors (FL1, FL2 and FL3) were appropriately tuned to characterize the dead and living cell population. Data were analyzed with Cell Lab Quanta Analysis software (Beckman Coulter). The cell concentration measured by flow cytometry was proven to be accurate up to a maximum of 2.7×10^7 cells mL⁻¹ by direct cell counting in a haemocytometer. Cell viability was determined by a fluorescence staining assay in diacetate (FDA) [35]. Cells stained with FDA were detected in the FL1 channel of the cytometer. The optimal FDA concentration and exposure time for the culture samples was 3×10^{-3} µg mL⁻¹ and 15 min, respectively. Values above these proved to be toxic.

2.6. Microalgal adhesion measurements

The microalgal adhesion intensity was evaluated using two procedures, which allowed us to monitor the distribution of biofouling on the glass slides. One of these was based on the *Chla* fluorescence of algae cells attached to the glass slide surface. (Chlorophyll *a* is the most widely used proxy for photosynthetic biomass biofilm [36]). Glass slides regularly removed from the photobioreactor were transferred into a flask filled with plenty of sterile Mediterranean seawater. The flask was static and the glass

slides, once submerged perpendicularly (axis Z) into it, were manually shaken carefully in the directions x-y at a maximum velocity of approximately 3 cm s^{-1} for around 10 seconds to remove non-adherent cells and debris. Next, the slides were placed on the reverse of a black polystyrene multi-well plate (96-wells; Nunclon®), on a surface equivalent in size to the slide surface, in which the bottom of the wells had been perforated. The total area of the holes accounted for a 44% of the slide surface. Then, the plate-slide assemblage was placed in a multi-well plate fluorescence reader (SynergyMx, BioTek® Instruments Inc., USA), in which the *Chla* fluorescence was excited at 480 nm and measured at 685 nm from the perforated wells in contact with the slide. The plate reader recorded fluorescence measurements from different points in each well. The measurements from all the wells were used to spatially represent the biofilm as contour plots. This method was validated as described below. Different volumes of culture samples were filtered through 0.45 cellulose acetate membrane filters (Sartorius Stedim Biotech GmbH, Germany) with a 1032 mm^2 filtration area. The cells were evenly deposited on filter surface. The cell densities (*CD*) obtained ranged from 0 to $4.5 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cells mm}^{-2}$. Filters were then placed on the reverse of a black polystyrene multi-well plate (96-wells; Nunclon®) as described above for glass slides, and *Chla* fluorescence measured. All experiments were performed in duplicate. A linear relationship between fluorescence intensity (*FI*) and *CD* was observed up to a *FI* value close to $9 \cdot 10^4$ relative units corresponding to a cell density of $1.92 \cdot 10^4 \text{ cells mm}^{-2}$ ($FI(\text{ru})=5.22 \cdot CD$; $r^2=0.989$). Higher cell densities can be measured by tuning the sensitivity of the fluorescence reader.

The other procedure was based on examining adhesion using epifluorescence microscopy. Glass slides removed from the photobioreactor were submerged in a 10 ng L^{-1} FDA solution and incubated in the dark at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for a period of 30 min to allow the

FDA to be taken up by the cells, which convert the non-fluorescent FDA into the green fluorescent metabolite fluorescein. Following this, the slides were washed with sterile filtered seawater and examined under a Nikon Eclipse 80i epifluorescence microscope (excitation at 482/35 nm; detection at 536/40 nm). For each slide, photomicrographs were taken at $\times 4$ magnification across the slide surface, at the same locations as those corresponding to the perforated wells, using a digital microscope camera (Tv Lens C-0.45X Nikon, JAPAN) interfaced with a PC operating Analysis® v.3.2 image software. Each image was 4.3 mm \times 3.4 mm in size. The total area covered by all the photomicrographs accounted for 18.7 % of the slide surface.

2.7. Thermodynamic approach and XDLVO model of the microalgal adhesion

Measurements of microalgal adhesion, contact angles, zeta potential and surface potential were used to estimate the cell-substrate and cell-cell interaction energies in accordance with the thermodynamic approach. The extended Derjaguin, Landau, Verwey, Overbeek (XDLVO) model was used [37]. This model's accuracy has been reported in explaining many studies regarding the selective surface adhesion of microbial cells [9] and microalgae [10, 11, 24]. Appendix I summarizes the mathematical formulations used for calculating, from experimental data, the free energies of cohesion, adhesion and co-aggregation (ΔG_{coh} , ΔG_{adh} and ΔG_{co-agg} , respectively) as well as the total interaction energy (G^{TOT}). In short, G^{TOT} indicates the degree of repulsion or attraction between surfaces: $G^{TOT} > 0$ favors repulsion and $G^{TOT} < 0$ favors adhesion. The degree of hydrophilicity and hydrophobicity of the algal surfaces were determined based on their free energy of cohesion: hydrophobic surfaces present $\Delta G_{coh} < 0$ (surface-surface interactions are stronger than surface-water interactions)

whereas for hydrophilicity, $\Delta G_{coh} > 0$. Similarly, adhesion and aggregation are favored at

$\Delta G_{adh} < 0$ and $\Delta G_{co-agg} < 0$, respectively.

2.8. Statistical analyses

One-way ANOVA test was used for significant difference analysis, by using Statgraphics centurion XVI statistical software (StatPoint, Herndon, VA, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effects of repeated ZP measurements

The methodology concerning ZP measurements for microorganisms is very complex due to the specific properties of cell membranes. Indeed, the ZP values of solid particles suspended in a well-defined liquid phase might be very different depending on the sample preparation and the device used [38]. The number of measurement repetitions, N , is also an important factor that can modify the ZP of the cells [39]. In this part of our study (see subsection 2.4), different samples of the same microalgal suspension were subjected to different N , ranging from 50 to 800. The variation of ζ_m and C with N is presented in Figure 3. ζ_m was maximal up to an N of 250 ($p < 0.05$, one way ANOVA test), dropping markedly from that, around 20%, relative to the maximum value, attaining a plateau value at an N of 300. This change cannot be attributed to C as it remained virtually constant ($p > 0.05$, one way ANOVA test), at around 39.6 mS cm^{-1} , in all the measurements (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Influence of the number (N) of repeated zeta potential measurements of the cells (ζ_m) on the mean value of ζ_m and electric conductivity (C) of the cell suspension. The dashed line represents the average value of C for all the runs. Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation (SD) for triplicate samples. Values denoted by a different lowercase at each point differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ in one-way ANOVA. When the DE bar is absent, the SD is smaller than the point. Conditions: $T = 26$ °C; $pH = 8 \pm 0.1$.

This suggests that an exposure time to the electric field above an N of 250-300 (equivalent to 3.8 min) may alter the physiological properties and/or damage microalgal cells in such a way that the cells' surface charge was modified. A few cellular responses, reported as being sensitive to many types of stresses in microalgae, were measured in order to confirm this hypothesis. Consequently, Figure 4 shows the effect of N on the $rETR/E$ curves and the corresponding photosynthetic parameters derived from equations (2) to (5). The $rETR_{max}$ value was significantly reduced above 300 N ($p < 0.05$, one way ANOVA test). On average, $rETR_{max}$ decreased to 4.6 % of the control value (i.e. the sample prior to the ZP measurement). The photosynthetic rate in the light-limited region (α) and the minimum saturating irradiance (E_k) were also considerably reduced (18.1 % and 25 % of the control values, respectively), indicating that the N

threshold is around 300 ($p < 0.05$, one way ANOVA test); above this number, an important inhibitor effect is observed on the photosynthetic activity.

Figure 4. (A) Photosynthesis-light response curves for *N. gaditana* estimated as relative electron transport rate ($rETR$) versus irradiances (E) by using the rapid light curve (RLC) technique. Each observation is a mean of two different experiments and solid line represent Eirler and Peeters' model results. (B) Variation of photosynthetic parameters, as determined by fitting using Eirler and Peeters model on RLCs, with the number of repeated measurements (N) for a given ζ_m determination. Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation (SD) for duplicate samples. When the DE bar is absent, the SD is smaller than the point. Conditions: $T^a = 26$ °C; pH = 8 ± 0.1 .

This pattern was likewise observed in the other measured cellular responses represented in Figure 5. The representation of F_v/F_m versus N in Figure 5A clearly shows the

separation of electrically-stressed cells from healthy cells at an N value around 300 (300) ($p < 0.05$, one way ANOVA test). Lethal effects of the applied electric field duration for this N threshold were also evident in the cell viability and cell count (see Fig. 5B) (300) ($p < 0.05$, one way ANOVA test). At the maximum N value applied, 800, almost 50% of the cell population disappeared, relative to the control, and all the remaining cells had a viability of less than 10%. As far as we know, these differences in the observed ZP (see Fig. 3) between completely active cells ($N < 100$) and non-viable cells ($N > 300$) have not been reported for microalgae. The only precedents refer to bacteria and cyanobacteria [39-41]. From a methodological point of view, changes in the cells' ZP attributable to biological changes originating from the measurement procedure should be identified operating under experimental conditions to rule out possible interferences.

3.2. The influence of ionic strength on surface zeta potential.

Figure 6 shows the ZP values of glass slides versus the negative logarithm of ionic strength (pI) of different seawater dilutions. The tracer particles used in all the dilutions were *N. gaditana* cells at the same concentration, 1.22×10^7 cells mL^{-1} . Negative zeta potential values were consistently observed throughout our experiments, which implies that the substrate surface was negatively charged. Absolute zeta potential values are in the 10 to 40 mV range, approximately, for an ionic strength range of 0.36 mM to 107.82 mM (i.e. equivalent to a C range of 0.03 to 9.06 mS cm^{-1}). The experimental results confirm that the zeta potential at the substrate surface (ψ_s) decreases as the pI value increases according to a very simple linear relationship:

$$\psi_s \sim pI \quad (7)$$

This linear relationship is the result of a convenient phenomenological approximation, and does not strictly follow cation adsorption thermodynamics and the structure of the

electrical double layer in the high- ψ_s limit, as discussed elsewhere [33]. This has been observed over a wide range of concentrations and solutions dominated by indifferent counterions [33].

Figure 5. Effect of the number of ζ_m repeated measurements on (A) the photosynthetic efficiency (F_v/F_m) of cells and (B) total cell concentration and viability. Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation (SD) for duplicate samples. Values denoted by a different lowercase at each point differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ in one-way ANOVA. When the DE bar is absent, the SD is smaller than the point. Conditions: $T^a = 26$ °C; $\text{pH} = 8 \pm 0.1$.

However, Equation (7) is very useful for engineering extrapolation. Note that our experimental methodology limits the ionic strength range ($I \leq 0.108$ M) within which ξ_m can be measured. On the one hand, the high counterion concentration almost entirely suppresses the influence of the surface charge resulting in low measurement signals that are hard to detect. On the other hand, the corresponding high sample conductivities trigger electrode reactions leading to electrolyte contamination, joule heating on electrodes and particles. Therefore, Equation (7) could be used for the theoretical prediction of ψ_s in a highly saline culture medium with high ionic strength values ($I \geq 0.108$ M).

Figure 6. Surface potential of glass slide (ψ_s) in contact with seawater dilutions plotted *versus* the negative logarithm of ionic strength (pI) of the dilutions. Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation (SD) for duplicate samples. Conditions: $T^a = 26$ °C; pH = 8 ± 0.1 .

3.3. Long-term cultivation experiment

N. gaditana was grown in the laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor illustrated in Figure 1. A representative sequential batch culture profile is shown in Figure 7. The run began as a batch culture (Stage 1) and the racks with glass slides were

immersed once the culture was in linear phase ($t=0$ in Fig. 7). The initial F_V/F_m value of around 0.7 remained constant until the fourth day of culture; just after starting the stationary phase with a cell concentration of around 10^8 cells mL^{-1} . In this growth phase F_V/F_m began to decline gradually reaching a value of nearly 0.6 on the eighth day of culture, after a further 3 days in the stationary phase. Nutrient limitation was confirmed at the end of Stage 1 by replenishing the culture with culture medium. This resulted in further growth (Stage 2, Fig. 7) and a complete F_V/F_m recovery over the following four days. Although there is no general consensus about this in relation to microalgae, F_V/F_m values of around 0.6 are indicative of healthy cells in *N. gaditana*. After eight days in Stage 2, the culture reached a new stationary phase with a final cell concentration of $\sim 2 \times 10^8$ cells mL^{-1} .

Figure 7. Sequential batch culture in the laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor. Temporal changes in cell concentration, the maximum photochemical yield of photosystem II (F_V/F_m), and the zeta potential of cells (ζ_m) are shown. Stage 1: initial batch culture; Stage 2: the culture was replenished with fresh medium; arrow indicates the instance of addition of nutrients. Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation for triplicate samples. When the DE bar is absent, the SD is smaller than the point.

Figure 7 also shows the zeta potential profile of the microalgal culture (ζ_m) determined during the cultivation process in order to preliminarily understand the physical intercellular interactions between the *N. gaditana* cells. As can be seen in Figure 7, *N. gaditana* presented a weak effective surface charge, ζ_m , ranging from -7.9 mV to -10.2 mV. Two factors could have contributed to this: a highly saline culture medium with a high ionic strength (the higher the ionic strength, the more compressed the double layer becomes—see section 3.2 in M&M) and the cell wall composition. Microalgal cell wall structure presents a significant interspecific variability. Cell walls are composed of polysaccharides, proteins and lipids. These constituents contain numerous functional groups such as carboxyl, hydroxyl, phosphoryl and amine groups, etc., which deprotonate with increasing pH providing the cell with a net negative surface charge. The cell wall of *Nannochloropsis* sp is composed of a bilayer structure consisting of a cellulosic inner wall protected by an outer hydrophobic algaenan layer [42]; i.e. a low electronegativity sheath material. Because *N. gaditana* has a low negative zeta potential, hypothetically, it will offer no force in preventing the cells coming together and flocculating.

The F_v/F_m and ζ_m profiles were virtually opposite; that is to say, when F_v/F_m decreased in Stage 1, ζ_m increased, and vice versa in Stage 2. In contrast to other results reporting a clear dependence on growth kinetics of microalgal cultures and the zeta potential of the cells [43, 44], our results show a link between F_v/F_m and ζ_m . Apparently, the physiological state, or metabolism, of the cells should be responsible for the electronegative nature of the microalgal cell surface. The growth rate should not be the only variable characterizing microalgal metabolism - F_v/F_m is the other widely-used parameter to determine the health of culture cells because its value may not be representative of the growth state.

3.4. Biofilm development of *N. gaditana* on the glass slides

Figure 8 displays the evolution of the *chla* fluorescence intensity distribution on the glass slides submerged in the LS-PBR batch culture. The microalga *N. gaditana* attached to the glass surface forming a biofilm which gradually increased across the slide surface until completely covering it after 20 days of culture. As the contour plots in Figure 8 show, cells did not attach evenly on the glass slides, indicating a heterogeneous distribution of biofilm thickness across the slide. The data for *chla* fluorescence intensity measured on each slide surface were averaged, and the mean value was used to obtain the biofilm growth dynamics as a function of culture time (see Fig. 8). The similarity of both growth curves, for freely-suspended cells (FSCs) in Fig. 7 and biofilm-embedded cells (BECs) in Fig. 8, is evident, with plateaus in the stationary states of both Stage 1 and 2. As observed for FSCs, BECs can grow under a nutrient-enriched medium, or have their growth limited if the nutrients are depleted. However, both growth curves are not synchronized because the growth modes of FSCs and BECs are different. For example, the characteristic times of mass transfer processes for FSCs in a perfectly mixed culture, as the LS-PBR is, are much smaller than for BECs. In addition, the biofilm formation period with actively growing BECs is on the days scale. This inevitably implies delayed growth dynamics for BECs in relation to those observed for FSCs. Therefore, the moments of appearance of the plateaus, and the duration of them, due to depletion of nutrients in the culture medium, are expected to be somewhat different in both growth curves.

Figure 8. Growth curves of *N. gaditana* biofilms in a sequential batch culture in the laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor, as followed by *chla* fluorescence intensity (FI) measurements averaged from different locations on the glass slide surface (calculations were described in section 2.6). Each point is represented by a different glass slide, removed from the photobioreactor at a given culture time. The inset contour plots are representative of the progression, intensity and distribution of the cell attachment on the glass slide surface.

Heterogeneity in the flow seemed to influence cell attachment distribution.

Slide racks were immersed in a zone where the culture gross flow pattern was descending (see Figure 1) and downsweeps of fluid reached the top of the racks just at the entrance of the space between slides. In accordance with previous studies [45, 46], cells may be convected to the slide surface by these downsweeps, favouring deposition of them towards on top of the slide surface in comparison with the remaining slide surface downstream where cells are subjected to a axial laminar flow originated due to the narrow space between slides (2 mm). On the other hand, when a descending flow, approaching the slide rack top at a certain mean velocity, hits the upper edge of the glass slides, a boundary layer of thickness δ begins to form close to the slide surface with a velocity gradient in a direction normal to flow. From fundamentals of fluid mechanics, it is known that this δ continuously increases downstream till that the fluid

reaches the status of “fully developed flow” (i.e. δ and velocity gradient remain unchanged) before leaving the space between slides. Since the width of the slide was small (2.6 cm), it is unlikely that the flow leaving the space between slides at the rack bottom had this status. If it is taken into account that the boundary layer thickness has a pronounced effect on mass transfer in biofilms [47], i.e. the lesser the value of δ the higher the mass transfer coefficient is, dissolved nutrient transport velocity to cells residing in biofilm close to the slide surface top was probably higher than in slide surface bottom. Finally, other factor that may have contributed to the spatially heterogeneous cell attachment pattern observed was the non-uniform flow field impinging on the slide rack top.

The slide rack system presented here can provide an interesting experimental platform for generating results on local-scale flow-biofilm or flow-adhesion interactions, and supply relevant information regarding the flow field at the centimeter-scale. The device may be used in a wide variety of configurations; the positioning of the racks inside the PBRs and spacing the slides as desired can allow many different flow patterns to be formed. Turbulent flow fields could be created by increasing the slide spacing and the air flow rate. The use of CFD techniques would help to expand the range of applications. The capability of customizing this device makes it particularly appropriate for evaluating new techniques to study and control biofilm growth and/or adhesion in PBRs. The device can also be used with a variety of cover slips and coupons, making it suitable for evaluating *in situ* the efficiency of anti-fouling coatings.

3.5. Dynamics of contact angles on the glass slide surface and algal lawns

Figure 9 displays the temporal variation of the CAs measured on the glass slides submerged in the PBR culture (Fig. 9A) and on the lawns of *N. gaditana* prepared from

samples of freely-suspended cells taken from the culture (Fig. 9B). A few mean CA values presented moderate standard deviation due to the heterogeneous distribution of biofilm characteristics across the slide or lawn surface, as observed in Fig. 8 for the biofilm thickness. The tendencies of the mean values revealed somewhat complex behavior on the surfaces. With regard to the glass slides, the water CA rose noticeably within the first four days from around 31° (hydrophilic in character) up to a maximum of 66° , typical of hydrophobic surfaces. The formamide CA varied in a similar way. After reaching maximum values, both CAs declined slowly, recovering the initial values after 20 days of culture. The diiodomethane CA did not follow an identifiable pattern. Clearly, the culture time induced substantial changes in the properties of the glass surfaces. During the first days of culture, a surface preconditioning phase probably occurred simultaneously to cell adhesion; in contrast, the covering of the glass surfaces by cell attachment and cell growth in the biofilm itself may have been significant in the second part of the culture.

To date, the reported studies on microalgal biofouling formation are scarce and the results are contradictory regarding the impact that solid surface wettability has on cell adhesion, which is correlated using the contact angle of a liquid via the Young equation [8]. One of the main drawbacks of all these studies is the short time scale of the adhesion experiments (2-24h) compared to the temporal operating scale of an industrial PBR (days to years). This is supported by our experimental results, in which over the first 24 h of culture, approximately, the CA values for each of the three test liquids remained virtually constant (data not shown). Taking into account the long-term results presented in Figure 9A, any relationship predicted between the contact angles of the substrate surface and the biofouling formation based on very short-term experiments may have led to misinterpretations.

Figure 9. Temporal variation of the contact angles measured on (A) glass slides submerged in the PBR culture and (B) lawns of *N. gaditana* prepared from broth samples withdrawn from the batch culture carried out in the laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor (see growth kinetics in Fig. 8). Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation for duplicate (A) and triplicate (B) samples.

Also the mean CAs of microalgal lawns, prepared as described in the Materials and Methods section, revealed a complex behavior of the algal surface over the duration of the culture (see Fig. 9B). CA values remained virtually constant up to day 12 of the culture, coinciding with the beginning of Stage 2 (see Fig. 7). From then onwards, the water and formamide CAs increased concomitantly. As far as we know, there is nothing

reported concerning the effect of the microalgal growth state on the contact angles measured in microalgal lawns. It is well-known that microalgae cultivation under nutrient deprivation influences the cell composition. This suggests that the changes experienced in culture medium composition during the batch culture may be a plausible reason for this effect. In this sense, our results are consistent with those reported for the microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* [12]. Lawns prepared from *C. vulgaris* cells grown in batch culture in a nutrient-limiting medium generally presented higher water and formamide CAs than cells cultured in a complete mineral medium.

3.6. Dynamics of free surface energies according to the thermodynamic model

The CA values for glass slides and microalgal lawns from Figure 9 were subsequently used to calculate changes in cohesion (ΔG_{coh}) and adhesion ΔG_{adh} free energies, as described in the Appendix. Figure 10 illustrates the influence of culture time on the value of these properties.

At the beginning of the culture (i.e., $t=0$), the ΔG_{coh} values for both substrate and microalgae displayed in Figure 10A were positive, indicating the hydrophilic character of both surfaces; although this was higher for the microalgal surface. According to the thermodynamic approach, hydrophilic repulsion would control the interaction between both surfaces. Additionally, the hydrophilicity of both surfaces resulted in dominant repulsive AB interactions against the weaker attractive LW interactions (see Fig. 10B). ΔG_{adh} was therefore positive at the initiation of the culture and, consequently, adhesion was not expected. This preliminary conclusion is untenable given that there was cell adhesion throughout the culture, as demonstrated in Figure 8.

After two days of culture, the substrate surface could be considered nearly amphiphilic because the ΔG_{coh} decreased to a value of 1.76 MJ.m⁻², close to zero (see

Fig. 10A). A week later, the substrate surface had acquired a strong hydrophobic character with a ΔG_{coh} value of -32.06 mJ m^{-2} . Apparently, this behavior could not be attributed to *N. gaditana* adhesion since the ΔG_{coh} value for the microalgal lawn was always clearly hydrophilic throughout the culture (see Fig. 10A). The additional adhesion of other materials with hydrophobic properties, whether excreted or not by *N. gaditana*, could have been responsible for this effect.

Two weeks later, the progressive adhesion and biofilm growth of *N. gaditana* were becoming prominent resulting in a sharp increase in the hydrophilic character of the substrate surface. On day 20 of the culture, most of the glass surface was completely covered with cells and thus, its free energy of cohesion was very close to that of the microalgal lawn (see Fig. 10A). This observation is relevant as it highlights the limitation of the surface thermodynamic theory in predicting cell adhesion under long-term cell-substrate interaction; accordingly, the prior selection of materials to minimize biofouling or promote adhesion *via* the thermodynamic theory does not seem a reliable procedure for microalgae.

The ΔG_{adh} dynamics (see Fig. 10B) were similar to that for ΔG_{coh} . The repulsive interaction AB is the main contributor in ΔG_{adh} , whereas the attractive interaction LW is insignificant throughout the culture time (this makes sense because the cell surface can have different groups that are able to exchange electrons). This is not fulfilled by day 8 of the culture, in which ΔG_{adh} drops sharply to a minimum close to zero. The explanation is similar to that given for Fig. 10A; that is, in the first week, when the surface changes from hydrophilic to hydrophobic (see Fig. 10AB), interactions due to component AB change from being repulsive (22.84 mJ m^{-2}) to slightly attractive (-1.04 mJ m^{-2}), while the LW interactions remain weakly attractive. Once again, the thermodynamic approach does not predict cell adhesion when applied at zero time;

although, it does so a week later. From the minimum value, the free energy of adhesion increases again due to increased cell coverage of the glass surface; until approaching the free energy of co-aggregation value for *N. gaditana* (16.88 mJ m⁻²), corresponding to the glass surface being totally coated by the cells.

Figure 10. (A) Change in the free energy of cohesion, ΔG_{coh} , and (B) change in the free energy of adhesion, ΔG_{adh} , sum of the AB and LW components, for both *N. gaditana* and glass surface, as a function of the culture time. The points framed with a dashed line in Fig. B represent the values of ΔG_{adh} and the corresponding AB, LW components for a glass surface completely coated by cells. Data points are averages, and vertical bars are standard deviation for duplicate samples (i.e. glass slides submerged in the PBR culture). Values denoted by a different lowercase at each point differ significantly at $p < 0.05$ in one-way ANOVA. When the DE bar is absent, the SD is smaller than the point.

3.7. The XDLVO approach

Figure 11 shows the time course of the EL, LW, AB, and total interaction energy, estimated from equations described in the Appendix, for the *N. gaditana*-glass system as a function of separation distance. Cell adhesion was also visualized by epifluorescence microscopy (see inset photos in Fig. 11). At culture time zero, decay along with the distance of the LW, EL and AB interaction energies is predicted. As can be seen, the influence of acid-base interactions is enormous ($4.15 \cdot 10^4 k_B T$ at a minimum separation distance, d_o , of 0.157 nm) compared to the EL and LW interactions. In this case, the AB interactions exerted their influence at distances almost as low as 8 nm and exponentially increased at shorter separation distances (see Fig. 11A). The repulsive EL interactions exerted their influence at much shorter separation distances (3.9 nm) and were too weak (about $89 k_B T$ at the minimum separation distance, d_o); this was due to the high ionic strength of the marine medium, which comprised the double electric layer surrounding the cell; and consequently weakened the repulsive electrostatic interaction between the solid surface and the cell. The LW interactions were attractive and dominant at long separation distances. The XDLVO model predicted a secondary minimum for the total interaction energy, G_{\min}^{TOT} , of around $-39.0 k_B T$ at a separation distance of 5.8 nm from the slide, in which there was a maximum attraction force, F_{\max}^{XDLVO} , calculated as the derivative of the total interaction energy, $G^{TOT}(d)$, at a distance of 5.8 nm. This cell attraction was due to the attractive LW forces which dominate the repulsive interaction forces EL and AB at greater separation distances. The Y and X axes in Figure 11 may also be representative of a hypothetical PBR wall made of glass and the separation distance from the PBR wall, respectively. Microalgae on the surrounding wall, moving in parallel to the PBR wall at a distance of 5.8 nm, with a kinetic energy greater than $39.0 k_B T$, would probably not adhere to the surface at

this secondary minimum. Energy barriers of this magnitude in flowing systems could be overcome by microalgal cells flowing at minimal velocities (v_{min}) of 3.14 mm s^{-1} (supposing spherical cell geometry with a density of 1 g mL^{-1}). Otherwise, the cell would most likely be attracted to the surface at this distance. The secondary minimum seems to play a critical role in explaining the reversible attachment of cells [48]. The cells can be loosely attached in the secondary minimum because of the high energy barrier between 5.8 nm and the wall surface. Besides the XDLVO forces, a *N. gaditana* cell at a distance of 5.8 nm from the tube wall is also subjected to a series of physical forces of different magnitudes, directions and sense: (i) gravitational force; (ii) lift forces generated by the fluid velocity gradient resulting from the fluid-dynamic conditions near the surface; and (iii) parallel-to-the-surface drag forces originating from the shear stress in the surface vicinity. The resultant net force for this force balance at each culture stage will determine if the cell finally adheres or not.

The XDLVO predictions above describe the total interaction energy between the microalgae-PBR surface, $G^{TOT}(d)$, and the respective components, right at the beginning of the culture. However, in the preceding sections it was demonstrated that the physico-chemical properties of both the microalgal cell surface and the PBR surface change over the culture period and, consequently, so will the total interaction energy, as shown in Fig. 11A-F. After two days, *N. gaditana* adhesion is almost imperceptible (Fig 11B). The G_{min}^{TOT} value at the secondary minimum is less negative than at time zero. The solid surface is less hydrophilic, as reported in Figure 10, and the adhesion forces between the microalgae cells and the glass are lower. The corresponding F_{max}^{XDLVO} value was lower as well. Unlike the thermodynamic approach, Figure 11A-B partially justifies the appearance of cell adhesion. *N. gaditana* cells in suspension inside the PBR will be transported by the liquid flow lines. In a pneumatically-agitated PBR, as used in this

experiment, the flow is heterogeneous. Therefore, at a local level, it is likely that a fraction of the cell population approaching the substrate surface at a given instant will have a velocity lower than the v_{min} value needed to overcome the corresponding F_{max}^{XDLVO} , and will thus be reversibly trapped in the secondary energy minimum. Simultaneously, the culture circulating in the vicinity of the glass slide at a velocity greater than v_{min} would detach a fraction of the cell population attached to the glass surface. Consequently, there would be equilibrium between the two attachment-detachment processes as a result of the flow. Apparently, this balance slightly favored attachment in the first two days, with minimal biofouling formation.

The type of profile for EL, LW, AB, and the total interaction energy observed in Figs. 11A-B, contrasts with that observed after the first week. At this stage in the culture, the XDLVO model predicted a primary adhesion minimum at the minimum separation distance (d_o) (i.e. an irreversible adhesion), and, consequently, a greater adhesion rate (there is no energy barrier) and a higher adhesion strength. By this point, the surface properties have radically changed following the formation of the conditioning biofilm, presumably because of attachment mediated by secretion, culture medium components and/or very few *N. gaditana* cells (fluorescence of the FDA-labeled biofilm showed an incipient amount of living *N. gaditana* cells attached to the glass). The observed increase in adhered cells is most probably due not only to the cells that were irreversibly trapped by the primary minimum but also the growth of new cells in the biofilm itself. Undoubtedly, this deviation from the expected pattern significantly determined biofouling progress. After two weeks (Fig. 11D), the slide surface recovers its hydrophilic character, with a secondary minimum appearing again, which is still less negative than at day two. This hydrophilic character is likely due to the attached *N. gaditana* cells themselves. As the culture progressed (3 weeks later, Fig. 11E), the

coupon became dirtier and is seen as the secondary minimum approaches that corresponding to a solid surface, which becomes fully covered in microalgal lawn (Fig. 11F) after 6 weeks of culture. The F_{max}^{XDLVO} and v_{min} values continued decreasing with culture time.

Figure 11. Dynamics of the interaction energy ($G(k_B T)$), as predicted by the XDLVO model, for the system *N. gaditana*-slides developed in a laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor operated in batch mode. Y-axis is presented in a reduced scale to better illustrate the magnitude and separation distance of the secondary energy minimum. The inset photos show the fluorescence of the film of FDA-labeled cells generated on the slides during the course of culture time.

4. Conclusions

The results showed that, from a methodological point of view, there is an exposure time threshold to the electric field supplied by the ZP meter - above which the photosynthetic parameters of *N. gaditana*, such as $rETR_{max}$, α , E_K and F_v/F_m , as well as cell concentration and viability, were negatively affected. This gave rise to changes in the ZP values measured in the same sample. A linear relationship between the ZP at the glass surface and the negative logarithm of the supernatant ionic strength (I) was observed. This equation can be used to reliably predict I in seawater-based culture media.

Long-term *N. gaditana* cultivation in a laboratory-scale, flat-panel PBR allowed us to demonstrate the existence of a link between the F_v/F_m and ZP of the cells but not to growth kinetics. The biofilm growth curve on the glass slides varied in a similar way to the growth kinetics followed by the freely-suspended cells in the PBR. This finding is compatible with the growth of a fraction of the attached cell population.

Although PBR flow heterogeneity influenced cell attachment distribution on the substrate surface, the slide rack system devised here offered an interesting and versatile experimental platform for generating results of local-scale flow biofilm or flow-adhesion interaction, providing relevant information about the PBR flow field at the centimeter-scale.

Contact angles on the glass slides and the algal lawns varied over the culture time. This greatly affected the calculated dynamics of surface free energies. This observation is relevant because the application of the thermodynamic theory failed to predict cell adhesion under long-term cultivation using the surface physico-chemical properties measured at the beginning of the culture. The XDLVO model could

satisfactorily explain reversible cell attachment based on the existence of a secondary minimum for the total interaction energy during most of the culture. The prediction of a primary energy minimum at day 8 of the culture would justify the irreversible cell adhesion observed.

The results presented here are potentially applicable to the design and manufacture of microalgal photobioreactors, whether adhesion is desired or not. They also provide a basis for other works studying the influence of algal biofilm growth factors.

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Appendix. List of the equations used to estimate the physicochemistry of microalgal adhesive interactions using the thermodynamic and XDLVO approaches.

1. Usage of the measured contact angles (θ) for calculating different surface free energies (γ)

$$\cos(\theta) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_{sr}^{LW} \cdot \gamma_l^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_l} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_{sr}^+ \cdot \gamma_l^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_l} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_{sr}^- \cdot \gamma_l^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_l} \quad \text{(Young's equation)} \quad (8)$$

Application to the microalgal mat surface (m)

$$\cos(\theta_{Dm}) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^{LW} \cdot \gamma_D^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_D} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^+ \cdot \gamma_D^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_D} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^- \cdot \gamma_D^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_D} \quad (9)$$

$$\cos(\theta_{Wm}) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^{LW} \cdot \gamma_W^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_W} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^+ \cdot \gamma_W^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_W} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^- \cdot \gamma_W^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_W} \quad (10)$$

$$\cos(\theta_{Fm}) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^{LW} \cdot \gamma_F^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_F} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^+ \cdot \gamma_F^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_F} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_m^- \cdot \gamma_F^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_F} \quad (11)$$

Application to the substrate surface (s)

$$\cos(\theta_{Ds}) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^{LW} \cdot \gamma_D^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_D} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^+ \cdot \gamma_D^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_D} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^- \cdot \gamma_D^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_D} \quad (12)$$

$$\cos(\theta_{Ws}) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^{LW} \cdot \gamma_W^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_W} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^+ \cdot \gamma_W^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_W} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^- \cdot \gamma_W^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_W} \quad (13)$$

$$\cos(\theta_{Fs}) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^{LW} \cdot \gamma_F^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_F} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^+ \cdot \gamma_F^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_F} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_s^- \cdot \gamma_F^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_F} \quad (14)$$

Bibliographic data [9]

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_D &= 50,8 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_F = 58 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_W = 72,8 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_D^{LW} = 50,8 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_F^{LW} = 39 \\ \text{mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_W^{LW} &= 21,8 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_D^+ = 0 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_F^+ = 2,28 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_W^+ = 25,5 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \\ \gamma_D^- &= 0 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_F^- = 39,6 \text{ mJ m}^{-2}; \gamma_W^- = 25,5 \text{ mJ m}^{-2} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Surface free energies calculated with equations and data from (9) to (15)

$$\gamma_m^{LW}; \gamma_s^{LW}; \gamma_m^+; \gamma_m^-; \gamma_s^+; \gamma_s^- \quad (16)$$

Surface free energies calculated from (16)

$$\gamma_m^{AB} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\gamma_m^+ \cdot \gamma_m^-} \quad (17)$$

$$\gamma_s^{AB} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\gamma_s^+ \cdot \gamma_s^-} \quad (18)$$

$$\gamma_m = \gamma_m^{AB} + \gamma_m^{LW} \quad (19)$$

$$\gamma_s = \gamma_s^{AB} + \gamma_s^{LW} \quad (20)$$

2. Degree of hydrophobicity and hydrophobicity of surfaces: free energy of cohesion

$$\Delta G_{coh}$$

$$\Delta G_{coh-s,m} = -2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{s,m}^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}})^2 - [4(\sqrt{\gamma_{s,m}^+ \cdot \gamma_{s,m}^-} + \sqrt{\gamma_W^+ \cdot \gamma_W^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_{s,m}^+ \cdot \gamma_W^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_{s,m}^- \cdot \gamma_W^+})] \quad (21)$$

3. Thermodynamic approach

Interaction substrate (s)-cell (m)

$$\Delta G_{adh}^{LW} = -2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_m^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_s^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}}) \quad (22)$$

$$\Delta G_{adh}^{AB} = 2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_m^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_s^+}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_m^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_s^-}) - 2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_m^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_m^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-}) - 2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_s^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_s^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-}) \quad (23)$$

$$\Delta G_{adh} = \Delta G_{adh}^{AB} + \Delta G_{adh}^{LW} \quad (24)$$

Interaction cell (m₁)-cell (m₂)

$$\Delta G_{co_agg}^{LW} = -2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_1}^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_2}^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}}) \quad (25)$$

$$\Delta G_{co_agg}^{AB} = 2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_1}^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_{m_2}^+}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_1}^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_{m_2}^-}) - 2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_1}^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_1}^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-}) - 2 \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_2}^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+}) \cdot (\sqrt{\gamma_{m_2}^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-}) \quad (26)$$

$$\Delta G_{adh} = \Delta G_{co_agg}^{AB} + \Delta G_{co_agg}^{LW} \quad (27)$$

4. XDLVO approach

Interaction substrate (s)-cell (m)— configuration - semi-infinite plate as opposed to a sphere

$$G^{LW}(d) = \frac{-A}{6} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{a}{d} + \frac{a}{d+2 \cdot a} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{d}{d+2 \cdot a} \right) \right] \quad (28)$$

$$A = -12 \cdot \pi \cdot d_0^2 \cdot \Delta G_{adh}^{LW} \quad (29)$$

$$G^{EL}(d) = \pi \cdot \varepsilon \cdot a \cdot (\psi_m^2 + \psi_s^2) \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot \psi_m \cdot \psi_s}{\psi_m^2 + \psi_s^2} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{1 + e^{-\kappa \cdot d}}{1 - e^{-\kappa \cdot d}} \right) + \ln(1 - e^{-2 \cdot \kappa \cdot d}) \right] \quad (30)$$

$$\psi_m = \zeta_m \cdot \left(1 + \frac{v}{a} \right) \cdot e^{\kappa \cdot v} \quad (31)$$

$$\kappa = \left[\frac{e^2 \cdot I \cdot 6.03 \cdot 10^{23}}{\varepsilon \cdot k_B \cdot T} \right]^{0.5} \quad \text{or} \quad \kappa = \left[\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon \cdot k_B \cdot T} \cdot \sum_i z_i^2 \cdot n_i \right]^{0.5} \quad (32)$$

$$G^{AB}(d) = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot a \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta G_{adh}^{AB} \cdot e^{-\frac{d_0-d}{\lambda}} \quad (33)$$

Interaction cell (m₁)-cell (m₂)—configuration - two interacting spherical cells

$$G^{LW}(d) = \frac{-A \cdot a_2 \cdot a_1}{6 \cdot d \cdot (a_2 + a_1)} \quad (34)$$

$$A = -12 \cdot \pi \cdot d_0^2 \cdot \Delta G_{co_agg}^{LW} \quad (35)$$

$$G^{EL}(d) = \frac{\pi \cdot \varepsilon \cdot a_2 \cdot a_1 \cdot (\psi_{m_1}^2 + \psi_{m_2}^2)}{a_2 + a_1} \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot \psi_{m_2} \cdot \psi_{m_1}}{\psi_{m_1}^2 + \psi_{m_2}^2} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{1 + e^{-\kappa \cdot d}}{1 - e^{-\kappa \cdot d}} \right) + \ln(1 - e^{-2 \cdot \kappa \cdot d}) \right] \quad (36)$$

$$G^{AB}(d) = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{a_2 \cdot a_1}{a_2 + a_1} \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta G_{co_agg}^{AB} \cdot e^{\frac{d_0 - d}{\lambda}} \quad (37)$$

$$\text{Total interaction energy} \quad (38)$$

$$G^{TOT} = G^{LW} + G^{EL} + G^{AB} \quad (39)$$

Nomenclature

Acronyms

CA	contact angle
DI	deionized water
FDA	fluorescein diacetate
LS-PBR	laboratory-scale flat-panel photobioreactor
RLC	rapid light curve
ZP	zeta potential

Variables and parameters

A	Hamaker's constant (J)
a	equivalent radius of the algal cell (m)
a_1	equivalent radius of the algal cell 1 (m)
a_2	equivalent radius of the algal cell 2 (m)
d	separation distance between two surfaces (m)
d_o	minimum separation distance between two surfaces equal to $0.157 \cdot 10^{-9}$ (m)
e	electron charge (C)
G	interaction energy (J m^{-2})
I	ionic strength of the medium (mol m^{-3})
k_B	Boltzmann's constant (J K^{-1})
n_i	concentration of ions of the species i in the solution ($\# \text{ m}^{-3}$)
N	number of measurement repetitions (-)
T	absolute temperature (K)
z_i	charge number of ions of the species i

F_V	maximum variable fluorescence of chlorophyll (au)
F_M	maximum fluorescence of chlorophyll (au)
F_0	initial fluorescence of chlorophyll (au)
C	electrolytic conductivity (mS cm^{-1})
$rETR$	relative electron transport rate ($\mu\text{mol e}^- \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
E	irradiance ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
E_k	saturating irradiance ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
N	number of repeated ZP measurements (-)
v_{min}	Minimal velocity of microalgae moving in parallel to the surrounding PBR to escape of a secondary energy minimum (G_{min}^{TOT}) calculated as $\sqrt{2 G_{min}^{TOT} /m_p}$, where m_p is the mass of the cell.
x_i	adjustment parameters for the model of Eilers and Peeters

Greek symbols

γ	surface free energy (J m^{-2})
ΔG	change in free energy (J m^{-2})
ε	dielectric constant of culture medium, i.e. seawater (F m^{-1})
ζ	zeta potential of a surface (V)
η	viscosity of the dispersing medium (pa.s)
θ	contact angle, °
κ	Inverse of double layer thickness (m^{-1})
λ	correlation length, i.e. gyration radius of water molecules in a solution. The λ value is equal to $0.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m for hydrophilic interaction. For hydrophobic interactions λ ranges from $1 \cdot 10^{-9}$ to $2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m as water molecules have a

larger gyration radius around hydrophobic surfaces. A value of $1.5 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m is adopted for this study for the hydrophobic attraction.

- ξ electrophoretic mobility ($\text{m}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
- ν hydration layer thickness associated with the algal cells (m). It changes inversely with the ionic strength of the medium and ranges from 3×10^{-11} m to 5×10^{-11} m. In this study a value of 3×10^{-11} m was used because of the high ionic strength of the seawater-based culture medium.
- ψ surface potential (V)
- α photosynthetic rate in the light-limited region ($\mu\text{mol}_e^- \mu\text{mol}_\text{photons}^{-1}$)

Superscripts

- AB* refers to acid–base, i.e. polar component
- EL* refers to electrostatic component
- LW* refers to Lifshitz–van der Waals, i.e. apolar or dispersive component
- TOT* refers to the total sum of the all components (*AB*, *EL*, *LW*)
- +
-
- refers to electron acceptor parameter
- refers to electron donor parameter

Subscripts

- adh* refers to adhesion
- co_agg* refers to co-aggregation
- coh* refers to cohesion
- D* refers to the probe liquid diiodomethane
- F* refers to the probe liquid formamide
- l* refers to probe liquid

<i>m</i>	refers to microalga
<i>max</i>	maximum
<i>s</i>	refers to substrate
<i>sr</i>	refers to any kind of surface
<i>W</i>	refers to the probe liquid water

References

- [1] H. Barberousse, R. Brayner, A.M.B. Do Rego, J.-C. Castaing, P. Beurdeley-Saudou, J.-F. Colombet, Adhesion of facade coating colonisers, as mediated by physico-chemical properties, *Biofouling* 23 (2007) 15-24.
- [2] R. Holland, T. Dugdale, R. Wetherbee, A. Brennan, J. Finlay, J. Callow, M.E. Callow, Adhesion and motility of fouling diatoms on a silicone elastomer, *Biofouling* 20 (2004) 323-329.
- [3] Y. Li, Y.H. Gao, X.S. Li, J.Y. Yang, G.H. Que, Influence of surface free energy on the adhesion of marine benthic diatom *Nitzschia closterium* MMDL533, *Colloids Surf. B. Biointerfaces* 75 (2010) 550-556.
- [4] P.J. Molino, E. Campbell, R. Wetherbee, Development of the initial diatom microfouling layer on antifouling and fouling-release surfaces in temperate and tropical Australia, *Biofouling* 25 (2009) 685-694.
- [5] P.J. Molino, R. Wetherbee, The biology of biofouling diatoms and their role in the development of microbial slimes, *Biofouling* 24 (2008) 365-379.
- [6] S. Schilp, A. Kueller, A. Rosenhahn, M. Grunze, M.E. Pettitt, M.E. Callow, J.A. Callow, Settlement and adhesion of algal cells to hexa (ethylene glycol)-containing self-assembled monolayers with systematically changed wetting properties, *Biointerphases* 2 (2007) 143-150.
- [7] M.S. Stanley, J.A. Callow, Whole cell adhesion strength of morphotypes and isolates of *Phaeodactylum tricorutum* (Bacillariophyceae), *Eur. J. Phycol.* 42 (2007) 191-197.
- [8] T. Young, TR, An assay on the cohesion of fluids, *Philos. Soc. Lond.*, 1805, pp. 65-87.

- [9] R. Bos, H.C. Van der Mei, H.J. Busscher, Physico-chemistry of initial microbial adhesive interactions—its mechanisms and methods for study, *FEMS Microbiol. Rev.* 23 (1999) 179-230.
- [10] A. Ozkan, H. Berberoglu, Cell to substratum and cell to cell interactions of microalgae, *Colloids Surf. B. Biointerfaces* 112 (2013) 302-309.
- [11] A. Ozkan, H. Berberoglu, Physico-chemical surface properties of microalgae, *Colloids Surf. B. Biointerfaces* 112 (2013) 287-293.
- [12] M. Sirmirova, G. Prochazkova, L. Siristova, Z. Kolska, T. Branyik, Adhesion of *Chlorella vulgaris* to solid surfaces, as mediated by physicochemical interactions, *J. Appl. Phycol.* 25 (2013) 1687-1695.
- [13] A.F. Ferreira, L.A. Ribeiro, A.P. Batista, P.A.S.S. Marques, B.P. Nobre, A.M.F. Palavra, P.P. da Silva, L. Gouveia, C. Silva, A biorefinery from *Nannochloropsis* sp. microalga - Energy and CO₂ emission and economic analyses, *Bioresour. Technol.* 138 (2013) 235-244.
- [14] J. Camacho-Rodríguez, M. Cerón-García, J. Fernández-Sevilla, E. Molina-Grima, Genetic algorithm for the medium optimization of the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* cultured to aquaculture, *Bioresour. Technol.* 177 (2015) 102-109.
- [15] E. Sierra, F.G. Acién, J.M. Fernández, J.L. García, C. González, E. Molina, Characterization of a flat plate photobioreactor for the production of microalgae, *Chem. Eng. J.* 138 (2008) 136-147.
- [16] M.E. Clares, J. Moreno, M.G. Guerrero, M. García-González, Assessment of the CO₂ fixation capacity of *Anabaena* sp. ATCC 33047 outdoor cultures in vertical flat-panel reactors, *J. Biotechnol.* 187 (2014) 51-55.

- [17] A. San Pedro, C. V. González-López, F. G. Acién, E. Molina-Grima, Outdoor pilot-scale production of *Nannochloropsis gaditana*: influence of culture parameters and lipid production rates in flat-panel photobioreactors, *Algal Res.* 18 (2016) 156-165.
- [18] R. K. Upadhyay, H. J. Pant, S. Roy, S. Liquid flow patterns in rectangular air-water bubble column investigated with radioactive particle tracking, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 96 (2013) 152-164.
- [19] E. Delnoij, J. A. M. Kuipers, W. P. M. Van Swaaij, Dynamic simulation of gas-liquid two-phase flow: effect of column aspect ratio on the flow structure. *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 52(21) (1997) 3759-3772.
- [20] J. J. J. Chen, M. Jamialahmadi, S. M. Li, Effect of liquid depth on circulation in bubble columns: a visual study, *Chem. Eng. Res. Des.* 67(2) (1989) 203-207.
- [21] F.G. Camacho, J.J.G. Rodríguez, A.S. Mirón, E.H. Belarbi, Y. Chisti, E.M. Grima, Photobioreactor scale-up for a shear-sensitive dinoflagellate microalga, *Process Biochem.* 46 (2011) 936-944.
- [22] J.M. Rocha, J.E. Garcia, M.H. Henriques, Growth aspects of the marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Biomol. Eng* 20 (2003) 237-242.
- [23] L. López-Rosales, J.J. Gallardo-Rodríguez, A. Sánchez-Mirón, M.d.C. Cerón-García, E.H. Belarbi, F. García-Camacho, E. Molina-Grima, Simultaneous effect of temperature and irradiance on growth and okadaic acid production from the marine dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum belizeanum*, *Toxins* 6 (2014) 229-253.
- [24] A. Ozkan, H. Berberoglu, Adhesion of algal cells to surfaces, *Biofouling* 29 (2013) 469-482.
- [25] Á.V. Delgado, F. González-Caballero, R. Hunter, L. Koopal, J. Lyklema, Measurement and interpretation of electrokinetic phenomena, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 309 (2007) 194-224.

- [26] R. Henderson, S. Parsons, B. Jefferson, Successful removal of algae through the control of zeta potential, *Sep. Sci. Technol.* 43 (2008) 1653-1666.
- [27] W.W. Wilson, M.M. Wade, S.C. Holman, F.R. Champlin, Status of methods for assessing bacterial cell surface charge properties based on zeta potential measurements, *J. Microbiol. Methods* 43 (2001) 153-164.
- [28] X. Quan, E.S. Fry, Empirical equation for the index of refraction of seawater, *Appl. Opt.* 34 (1995) 3477-3480.
- [29] L. Klein, C.T. Swift, An improved model for the dielectric constant of sea water at microwave frequencies, *IEEE Trans. Antennas. Propag.* 25 (1977) 104-111.
- [30] A.J. White, C. Critchley, Rapid light curves: a new fluorescence method to assess the state of the photosynthetic apparatus, *Photosynth. Res.* 59 (1999) 63-72.
- [31] P. Eilers, J. Peeters, A model for the relationship between light intensity and the rate of photosynthesis in phytoplankton, *Ecol. Model.* 42 (1988) 199-215.
- [32] J.C. Corbett, F. McNeil-Watson, R.O. Jack, M. Howarth, Measuring surface zeta potential using phase analysis light scattering in a simple dip cell arrangement, *Colloids Surf. Physicochem. Eng. Aspects* 396 (2012) 169-176.
- [33] B.J. Kirby, E.F. Hasselbrink, Zeta potential of microfluidic substrates: 1. Theory, experimental techniques, and effects on separations, *Electrophoresis* 25 (2004) 187-202.
- [34] B.J. Kirby, E.F. Hasselbrink, Zeta potential of microfluidic substrates: 2. Data for polymers, *Electrophoresis* 25 (2004) 203-213.
- [35] X. Xiao, Z.-y. Han, Y.-x. Chen, X.-q. Liang, H. Li, Y.-c. Qian, Optimization of FDA-PI method using flow cytometry to measure metabolic activity of the cyanobacteria, *Microcystis aeruginosa*, *Phys. Chem. Earth Pt. A/B/C* 36 (2011) 424-429.

- [36] M.W. Skov, M. Volkelt-Igoe, S.J. Hawkins, B. Jesus, R.C. Thompson, C.P. Doncaster, Past and present grazing boosts the photo-autotrophic biomass of biofilms, *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 401 (2010) 101-111.
- [37] C.J. van Oss, The Extended DLVO Theory, in: C.J.v. Oss (Ed.), *The Properties of Water and their Role in Colloidal and Biological Systems*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2008, pp. 31-48.
- [38] M. Kosmulski, E. Małczka, W. Janusz, J.B. Rosenholm, Multiinstrument study of the electrophoretic mobility of quartz, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 250 (2002) 99-103.
- [39] J. Cieśla, A. Bieganski, M. Janczarek, T. Urbanik-Sypniewska, Determination of the electrokinetic potential of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bv trifolii Rt24. 2 using Laser Doppler Velocimetry—A methodological study, *J. Microbiol. Methods* 85 (2011) 199-205.
- [40] K.A. Soni, A.K. Balasubramanian, A. Beskok, S.D. Pillai, Zeta potential of selected bacteria in drinking water when dead, starved, or exposed to minimal and rich culture media, *Curr. Microbiol.* 56 (2008) 93-97.
- [41] R.E. Martinez, O.S. Pokrovsky, J. Schott, E.H. Oelkers, Surface charge and zeta-potential of metabolically active and dead cyanobacteria, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 323 (2008) 317-325.
- [42] J. Sun, J. Cheng, Z. Yang, K. Li, J. Zhou, K. Cen, Microstructures and functional groups of *Nannochloropsis* sp. cells with arsenic adsorption and lipid accumulation, *Bioresour. Technol.* 194 (2015) 305-311.
- [43] M.K. Danquah, B. Gladman, N. Moheimani, G.M. Forde, Microalgal growth characteristics and subsequent influence on dewatering efficiency, *Chem. Eng. J.* 151 (2009) 73-78.

- [44] A. Ahmad, N.M. Yasin, C. Derek, J. Lim, Crossflow microfiltration of microalgae biomass for biofuel production, *Desalination* 302 (2012) 65-70.
- [45] C. A. Kent, Biological fouling: basic science and models, in: L.F. Melo, T.R. Bott, C.A. Bernardo (Eds.), *Fouling Science and Technology*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, 1988, pp. 207-222.
- [46] M.G. Brading, J. Jass, H.M. Lappin-Scott, Dynamics of bacterial biofilm formation, in: H.M. Lappin-Scott, J.W. Costerton (Eds.), *Microbial biofilms*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1995, pp. 46-63.
- [47] H. Horn, S. Lackner, Modeling of Biofilm Systems: A Review, *Adv. Biochem. Eng. Biotechnol.* 146 (2014) 53-76
- [48] H. Wang, M. Sodagari, Y. Chen, X. He, B.-m.Z. Newby, L.-K. Ju, Initial bacterial attachment in slow flowing systems: effects of cell and substrate surface properties, *Colloids Surf. B. Biointerfaces* 87 (2011) 415-422.